

REGISTRY OF SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS/META-ANALYSES DETAILS

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Title

Knowledge sharing for sustainable development in agriculture: A systematic literature review and narrative synthesis.

Key Review Question and Objectives

The main objectives of the present systematic review are to: (1) identify through a systematic literature search, (2) provide a description of the characteristics, and (3) appraise existing evidence on all knowledge sharing approaches used in primary research studies for the promotion of agricultural sustainability.

Lay Summary (please do not just paste your abstract. Please summarise your research, written in a way the public can understand)

The adoption of sustainable agricultural practices can generate socio-economic and environmental benefits which can provide solutions to the growing demands for food and other resources to sustain the human population now and in the future (Adenle, Azadi, & Manning, 2018; Velten, Leventon, Jager, & Newig, 2015). There is increasing recognition that interaction and participatory approaches to learning, both multi-actor and peer-to-peer, can generate new knowledge that has the potential to contribute to the achievement of agricultural sustainability goals and impacts (Dolinska & d'Aquino, 2016; Schut et al., 2016). However, existing evidence on such approaches has not yet been systematically identified and evaluated. The present systematic review therefore aims to address this gap in the scientific literature.

Primary research studies reporting on knowledge sharing approaches addressing agricultural sustainability will be identified through searching four bibliographic databases from inception to May 2021, using search terms combining subject headings and free-text terms. Retrieved records will be independently screened by two reviewers for inclusion. Decisions on eligibility will be based on a priori specified criteria. Included publications and will be subsequently assessed for methodological quality using a

standardised checklist. Findings will be narratively synthesised and presented in descriptive summaries of relevant outcomes. The review will be reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guideline (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff, & Altman, 2009).

Does this Systematic Review include a Meta-Analysis?

No

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Countries involved

Greece

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Search Strategy

The search strategy will comprise five steps. An initial scoping search will be conducted in Google Scholar and Scopus to identify primary research studies reporting on knowledge sharing approaches in agriculture. Relevant text words contained in the title, abstract and authors' keywords of

identified papers, and database index terms, will be compiled to produce a list of search terms. Four bibliographic databases will be then searched using a combination of subject headings and free-text terms based on the search terms previously identified, adjusted for each database. Once eligible papers are located, a thorough backward (through hand-searching reference lists) and forward (using Google Scholar) citation search will be performed. Furthermore, a combination of strategies including searching trial databases, grey literature databases and websites of relevant organisations will be employed to locate evidence published outside of the traditional publishing and distribution channels. Lastly, the authors of eligible conference abstracts will be contacted for full-text publications.

Information Sources (describe all information sources (e.g., databases with dates of coverage, contact with study authors to identify additional studies) in the search and dates you will or last searched)

The following databases will be searched from first record published until May 2021: (1) Scopus; (2) Web of Science; (3) AGRICOLA; (4) Sociological Abstracts (via ProQuest). In addition, the OpenGrey, WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform, and CENTRAL databases will be searched to identify any literature not published through traditional means (i.e., “grey literature”). Authors of included papers will be contacted where information relevant to the review is missing.

Inclusion Criteria

Articles will be included if they meet all the following criteria: (1) Reporting on empirical studies (prospective or retrospective, qualitative or quantitative); (2) Reporting evidence on knowledge sharing approaches (peer to peer or multi-actor) addressing at least one of the sustainability dimensions (i.e., social, economic, and/or environmental) as defined by Asadi and colleagues (2013); (3) Studies are conducted within the agricultural sector; adopting a broad approach to the definition of “agriculture” that encompasses a wide range of activities in which natural resources are used for the production of food and other secondary products that sustain the global human population (Harris & Fuller, 2014).

Exclusion Criteria

Articles will be excluded if they: (1) Report on non-primary studies, including systematic reviews, opinion articles, editorials or book chapters; (2) Report on approaches to knowledge exchange that are unrelated to agricultural sustainability; (3) Are not written in English.

Condition, disease or problem being studied

Information/knowledge exchange on issues relating to sustainable development in agriculture.

Patients/Participants/Population

Stakeholders or actors in the agricultural sector.

Intervention(s) or Exposure(s)

Approaches to the exchange and sharing of knowledge for the promotion of sustainable agriculture.

Control or Comparator(s)

All studies meeting eligibility criteria regardless of the research design employed will be included in the review. Eligible studies with control groups for comparison (if any) will be therefore included as well.

Primary Outcomes

The primary outcomes of this review will be the (1) identification, (2) narrative description of characteristics, and (3) appraisal of existing evidence on knowledge sharing approaches addressing sustainable development in the agricultural sector.

Secondary Outcome(s)

N/A

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Two reviewers will extract data independently on each study and on the characteristics of each knowledge sharing approach using a standardised form developed for the purposes of this review. For each study, the following information will be extracted and entered into the form: author(s), year of publication, country of origin, study aim(s), design, setting, sample size, and relevant findings reported. For each approach identified, extracted data will include: name and type of the approach used, aim/purpose for which it was employed, actors/stakeholders involved, and documented impact. The results of data extraction will be compared and any disagreements between reviewers will be resolved by consensus.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

Due to heterogeneity of the study types eligible for inclusion, the Quality Assessment for Diverse Studies (QuADS) (Harrison, Jones, Gardner, & Lawton, 2021) tool will be used to appraise the methodological and reporting quality of the included studies, and overall body of evidence. QUADS is a revised version of an established quality appraisal tool, the Quality Assessment Tool for Studies with Diverse Designs (QATSD) (Sirriyeh, Lawton, Gardner, & Armitage, 2012) with demonstrated validity

and reliability. Two reviewers will independently score all included studies for methodological quality. Scores will be compared, and any discrepancies will be resolved through discussion.

Data Synthesis Strategy

A considerable heterogeneity in terms of design, methods, and types of reported outcomes was observed across potentially eligible papers identified through the scoping database search, limiting therefore the ability to conduct a meta-analysis/meta-synthesis of reported outcomes. Instead, relevant data on study and knowledge sharing approach characteristics, and reported study outcomes extracted from included publications will be narratively synthesised following Cochrane's framework for data synthesis in systematic reviews (McKenzie, Brennan, Ryan, Thomson, & Johnston, 2020).

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

Reported information and relevant data on studies and knowledge sharing approaches will be categorised into groups of similar characteristics, and comparisons will be made between and across groups and subgroups.

Dissemination plan

At least one paper relating to findings from this review will be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal. Findings may be also presented in abstracts submitted to academic conferences.

Stage of Review at Time of Submission

Protocol Written, Preliminary searches

Post Review Results (once available)

References

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